

Santal

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Entry tags: Indic Religious Traditions, Religious Group

The largest of South Asia's tribal populations, the Santals live in the Indian states of Bihar, West Bengal, and Orissa (Carrin-Bouez and Beierle, 1998). Christian missionaries arrived in the region around the mid-1800's, but found little success in conversion attempts. The Santal religion is primarily concerned with numerous spirits/deities known as Bongas, which are of various classes (such as clan, village, family, and specific places). A high god is present but otiose. The village priest (Ato Naeke) and his assistant (Kudam Naeke) are responsible for communicating with the supernatural realm, as well leading communal religious ceremonies. In addition to the Ato Naeke and Nudam Naeke are other practitioners, such as the hunt-priest (Dehri), herbalist/medicine man, Bonga-doctor (Ojha), and witch detector (Jan guru) (Biswas, 1956:107). Religious practitioners (mainly the village priest) typically work with the village headmen. Because the Santal religious beliefs and practices are bound up with many aspects of society, this entry considers the Santal religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. This entry focuses specifically on the Bankura and Birbhum districts of Bengal, around the time of 1940.

Date Range: 1915 CE - 1940 CE

Region: Bankura and Birbhum districts of Bengal

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Western India

Bankura and Birbhum districts of Bengal, ca. 1940

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw42-005>
- Source 1 Description: Culshaw, W. J. (1949). *Tribal Heritage: A Study Of The Santals*. *Missionary Research Series*. London: Lutterworth Press.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw42-003>

– Source 2 Description: Mukherjea, C. (1962). Santals. Calcutta: A. Mukherjee & Co., Private Ltd.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw42-004>

– Source 3 Description: Biswas, P. C. (1956). Santals Of The Santal Parganas. Delhi: Bharatiya Adimjati Sevak Sangh.

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw42-000>

– Source 1 Description: Carrin-Bouez, M., & Beierle, J. (1998). Culture Summary: Santal. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Christian missionaries arrived in the Santal's region around the mid-1800's. "Although progress has been relatively more rapid in some areas than in others, it remains true everywhere that only a small proportion of the Santals has entered the Christian Church; on the other hand, in comparison with the non-Christian communities who are their immediate neighbours, the Santals have proved responsive" (Culshaw, 1949:163). "The influence of the Hindus living nearby saturates the thoughts and ideas of the Santals, and when we remember that ethnologically many of these Hindus were aboriginals in origin, we can find out the reasons why many Santals are really anxious to describe themselves as Hindus like their neighbours. In their rural settlements, one can find the Santals joining the worship of the Hindu gods and goddesses like Durga, Kali and Mahadev. Like the rest of the Hindus, they salute these deities and the entire tribe dance and amuse themselves during these ceremonies" (Mukherjea, 1962:55).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 1654, Pacification, the Santal were pacified before the 25-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 1654, Pacification, the Santal were pacified before the 25-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the Santal religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is no process for assigning religious affiliation beyond being born into a particular clan.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the recruitment of new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "The Headman with the assembly decides all matters of a socio-religious, legal and quasi-legal nature of the village. They are the fountain-heads of justice and custodians of Santal customs and manners, the first court of law both civil and criminal, for the Santal is generally averse to litigation in legally constituted courts, and prefers the arbitration of his village-elders" (Mukherjea, 1962:155).

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The village headman and village priest are typically two separate individuals (see Mukherjea, 1962:152).

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, there is some overlap between political and religious leaders (Ross, 1983; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The attitude of the community towards the family or the individual who has become Christian is a complex of tolerance and incomprehension. Becoming a Christian is not in itself an offence for which there is an established penalty in tribal custom: the village council does not act and there is no formal outcasting of the offender from the community as there is, for example, when a Santal has married outside the tribe" (Culshaw, 1949:170).

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Culshaw, 1949:170

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population,

numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 178656

Notes: "So far as Bengal is concerned, the Santals numbered...796,656 in 1931...In regard to their religion, it is noticeable that while in 1921 only 158,383 were returned as Hindus and 553,657 under tribal religions, the Census figures of 1931 returned 433,502 as Hindu Santals and 352,386 as following tribal religions. The result is seen in an increase of Hindu Santals from 22.2 per cent of the total to almost 54.5 per cent. This phenomenal increase of Hindu Santals is explained as due to the missionary activities of the Hindu Mission and the natural increase in the number of Hindus in the tribe" (Mukherjea, 1962:61). More specifically, Mukherjea (1962:62) notes that according to the Census Report of 1931, 64,079 Santals were living in Birbhum, and 114,577 in Bankura.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Santal village is organized to secure the greatest possible degree of co-operation not only in temporal affairs but also in dealing with the spirit world. The relationship between Santal society and some part of the universe inhabited by spirits is very close, and it is maintained by the society acting through its representatives. One of the most important officials in the village is the naeke, or village priest, whose business it is to maintain right relationships with the tribal spirits" (Culshaw, 1949:78). "Amongst the Santals working in the Daminiko area where they are closely concentrated, it was curious to notice many functionaries named as Ojha, Janguru, Kamruguru, Raranic, Ato-Naike, Kudam Naike and Dehri. The Santal carefully draws a distinction between the officers of his social ceremonials, the high priests of the community and the specialists who may be described in modern terms as the practising physicians and the mental disease experts, the last of course not being psychopaths but masters of spiritualist seances. The sorcerer who practises evil eye and witchcraft is also sharply distinguished" (Biswas, 1956:108).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Mukherjea, 1962:284

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: "When the priest dies childless or resigns voluntarily, village elders assemble at the house of the Headman or the priest. Next, the six deities of holy grove are invoked by the men sitting on mats, each with a winnowing-fan and some sun-dried rice given by the priest, if he is resigning, or by the Headman, if the priest is dead. As usual some begin to shake their heads in a hypnotic trance and get possessed. These men in trance are asked as to who they are. They name themselves after the gods they stand for. Thereafter, they are questioned as to whom they are recommending for the post. They answer. But it is customary that Maran Buru will first propose a name, and the other actor-deities invariably second and support him" (Mukherjea, 1962:284).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: "Should he [the village priest] commit any social wrong, he can be removed from office by the tribal assembly" (Mukherjea, 1962:284).

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Should he [the village priest] commit any social wrong, he can be removed from office by the tribal assembly" (Mukherjea, 1962:284).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture among the Santal.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972, column 6; note, identical to SCCS Variable 66).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "The Santal lives in harmony with the surroundings, having no temple and stooping to no idol made by his hand for the purpose of worship" (Biswas, 1956:103).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "Santal worship centres round its sacred places, the most prominent of which is the jaher, the sacred grove usually to the west of the village. It consists of a number of tall, slim sarjom trees with perhaps one or two trees of other varieties, the whole having been left standing since the village was first founded" (Culshaw, 1949:80).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Culshaw, 1949:80

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "When after a man's death, his jan baba (bones) are thrown into the sacred river. Damodar, his mul (shadow, soul) goes up to Serma disom or Svòròg (Heaven). There it is that the virtuous ones remain, enjoying heavenly bliss along with the gods themselves" (Mukherjea, 1962:228). "Those who were sinners on the earth, are consigned to Nòròk (Hell). It is a very painful place where big worms feed perpetually on those thus punished, and a variety of other tortures are also provided..." (ibid. p.229).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The Heaven (Serma disom, lit. sky-country) is situated up in the blue skies. It is also called Svòròg. There the gods, Maran Buru (the Chief Presiding Deity) and others live. At times they also come down to earth. When after a man's death, his jan baba (bones) are thrown into the sacred river. Damodar, his mul (shadow, soul) goes up to Serma disom or Svòròg (Heaven). There it is that the virtuous ones remain, enjoying heavenly bliss along with the gods themselves" (Mukherjea, 1962:228). "Those who were sinners on the earth, are consigned to Nòròk (Hell). It is a very painful place where big worms feed perpetually on those thus punished, and a variety of other tortures are also provided..." (ibid. p.229).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details regarding the spatial location of the afterlife.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Mukherjea, 1962:228

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "As regards the period of such punishment and re-birth on earth for those who are consigned to Hell, some believe that they are born again as beasts and birds on the earth. But if their sin is washed away completely, they can have re-birth as men. Others are disposed to believe that the sinners never come back to earth as men, but only as birds and beasts" (Mukherjea, 1962:229).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Mukherjea, 1962:229

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Mukherjea, 1962:229

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Cremation is the almost universal rule, although there are certain significant exceptions. Children who die before puberty are buried with little ceremony in shallow graves on the edge of the forest, and though thorns are placed over the grave to protect the body from wild animals, such graves are often disturbed. Men and women who have died from certain diseases are buried in the same manner..." (Culshaw, 1949:150).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "Those at the cremation ground now procure fuel and make the pyre. The dead body is taken round thrice and placed on it...the son of the deceased sets fire to the body, by lighting the straw of the thatch taken from the house of the deceased. The members of the tribe present throw some fuel each on the pile on fire as their ceremonial duty on behalf of the clan"

(Mukherja, 1962:221).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Cremation is the almost universal rule, although there are certain significant exceptions. Children who die before puberty are buried with little ceremony in shallow graves on the edge of the forest, and though thorns are placed over the grave to protect the body from wild animals, such graves are often disturbed. Men and women who have died from certain diseases are buried in the same manner..." (Culshaw, 1949:150).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: "On the conclusion of the cremation, water is poured on the pyre, first by the man who

sets fire to the body, next by the pall-bearers and lastly by all the members of the tribe present. A bone from the forehead of the deceased is now gathered and kept inside the earthen pot, specially carried for the purpose, and buried under the earth near a sal -tree" (Mukherjea, 1962:223). "Next, the bones previously buried are carried to the cross-road, washed with water and hândia ràsi (the best part of rice-beer), being rubbed within the folds of a yellow-coloured cloth. The women offer presents of money to the bone, and it is placed inside the sack prepared for the purpose. The empty pot (which contained the bone so long), is now placed on three twigs of Kendu tree (called so in Oriya) while the carrier walks round it thrice and then facing cast breaks it amidst cries of Horibol by the village-elders. Thereafter, he leaves for his destination being escorted by two men to the Gadi (halting place for men going towards Damodar)...After the jan baha (the bones of the dead) are deposited in the Damodar river, offerings like the Pindòs of the Hindus are prepared with mud, toothpicks, parched rice and sweet-meats on three sal -leaves on an altar, when Maran Buru, the dead ancestors and the deceased are propitiated" (Mukherjea, 1962:227).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "Those at the cremation ground now procure fuel and make the pyre. The dead body is taken round thrice and placed on it. A fowl is sacrificed by means of a twig of a mòhua tree passed through its eyes, and hung on one of the posts round the pyre" (Mukherjea, 1962:221).

Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "Those at the cremation ground now procure fuel and make the pyre. The dead body is taken round thrice and placed on it. A fowl is sacrificed by means of a twig of a mòhua tree passed through its eyes, and hung on one of the posts round the pyre" (Mukherjea, 1962:221).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not present; cremation is the preferred method for disposing corpses.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Formal burials are not present, rather, cremations are held for the dead. (See Mukherjea, 1962:220-223).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings include a supreme high god, ancestral spirits, household and tutelary spirits, the hunting spirit, village deities, boundary spirits, and others (see Biswas, 1956:135 and questions below for more details).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], indicates that a high god is present but otiose or not concerned with human affairs (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). "Coming now to the Santals we find almost all the authorities agreeing in conceding to them the idea of a supreme being. But there is a great diversity of opinion as to what he is called" (Biswas, 1956:102).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: There is no monarch among the Santal.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: There is no monarch among the Santal.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Mukherjea (1962:3) indicates that the supreme deity Thàkur Jiu, is "too good to

interfere with men, and is a passive deity after all."

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "For the most part, belief in a Supreme Being is not operative. He is frequently mentioned in conversation as the source of good and bad weather, and also of good and bad health; it is common to hear such expressions as 'By the mercy of Cando we are well' and 'If Cando has mercy we shall obtain good crops'. By such means do Santals acknowledge that all their magic, their prayers and their hard work are an insufficient guarantee that they will attain their heart's desire and that God's ways are inscrutable" (Culshaw, 1949:91).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: Mukherjea (1962:3) indicates that the supreme deity Thàkur Jiu, is "too good to interfere with men, and is a passive deity after all."

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirits of dead ancestors are placed by the Santals in a separate class by themselves" (Biswas, 1956:135). "The Santal religion is also not a little concerned with ancestral and certain other disembodied souls and Nature-spirits and deities. The rites employed to establish relations with them are mainly supplications and prayers, offerings of sacrifices and the ceremonial sharing of sacrificial food besides certain special observances and taboos" (Biswas, 1956:104).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Santals have several village spirits, whom they worship during all public festivals. They are supposed to preside over particular rural areas in which they live" (Mukherjea, 1962:274). "Apart from the village-spirits mentioned before, the Santals people their hills with numerous super-human agencies, called Pats. These powers inspire them with a fear and naturally, they are propitiated so that they may not do the Santals any harm" (Mukherjea, 1962:277). "Santals have about a number of mischievous minor spirits, who find a devilish delight in bringing epidemics to men or cattle, unless propitiated with appropriate rituals" (Mukherjea, 1962:281).

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst lesser Bongas under this head, mention should be made of Acracli Bonga (or Jodhe Bonga as in Mayurbhanj), who presides over the interests of married women. We were told that if a woman steals anything from her parents' home, and takes it to her husband's place, this godling maintains a close watch over the stolen properties and punishes the household by bringing illness and even death" (Mukherjea, 1962:282).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Thus in religion proper the main attitude of Santal Society towards the supernatural, is one of reverential fear in the presence of certain mysterious supernatural powers and beings and dependence on and propitiation to and prayerful submission to them, and the result expected is the averting of the ill-will and securing the good will of the supernatural beings and good luck to man in crops and cattle, health and progeny" (Biswas, 1956:104).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The bongas are friendly beings at times, but most often mischievous and naughty elves playing mischievous pranks with men, bringing them trouble and causing misery at times. These bongas are supposed at times to harass humanity, to eat people (as the Santals express it) because they are hungry, displeased, hurt or envious, and this eating is the devouring of health and substance of the person exposed to the displeasure of the spirits" (Biswas, 1956:103).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "The bongas are friendly beings at times, but most often mischievous and naughty elves playing mischievous pranks with men, bringing them trouble and causing misery at times. These bongas are supposed at times to harass humanity, to eat people (as the Santals express it) because they are hungry, displeased, hurt or envious, and this eating is the devouring of health and substance of the person exposed to the displeasure of the spirits" (Biswas, 1956:103).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "It is very difficult to attempt a classification of the orders of the supernatural beings which constitute the religious belief of a community. The classification would often imply the existence of a notion of hierarchy of the supernatural beings, one being far superior to the rest. It is curious to observe that this supreme being is never worshipped in the faith that he can never work out any evil. As for the rest the rank may be determined in the order in which worship is offered to them. But here again the difficulty would lie in the fact that a particular occasion would demand predominance being given to particular spirits. Thus the classification would be more or less a division in parallel lines, for it would be hard to decide the superiority or inferiority of the ancestral spirits on the one hand and the departmental deities of nature on the other" (Biswas, 1956:134).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The code of behaviour between relatives is sanctioned by a belief that any infringement of its provisions will result in retaliation by the spirits, who cause such diseases as leprosy, or who will inflict dire punishment after death and make it impossible for funeral ceremonies to be duly carried out" (Culshaw, 1949:88).

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "The code of behaviour between relatives is sanctioned by a belief that any infringement of its provisions will result in retaliation by the spirits, who cause such diseases as leprosy, or who will inflict dire punishment after death and make it impossible for funeral ceremonies to be duly carried out" (Culshaw, 1949:88).

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Spirit intrusion (evil bonga spirits) occurs when an individual has breached a taboo (see Biswas, 1956:115).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding supernatural punishment.

Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on the agents of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The Santal's high god is otiose and not concerned with the affairs of humans.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits (bongas) are referred to as the agents of supernatural punishment (see Culshaw, 1949:88)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The code of behaviour between relatives is sanctioned by a belief that any infringement of its provisions will result in retaliation by the spirits, who cause such diseases as leprosy, or who will inflict dire punishment after death and make it impossible for funeral ceremonies to be duly carried out" (Culshaw, 1949:88).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: (Culshaw, 1949:88)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Those who were sinners on the earth, are consigned to Nòròk (Hell). It is a very painful place where big worms feed perpetually on those thus punished, and a variety of other tortures are also provided (e. g. they may be ordered to unweave the knots of a net)" (Mukherjea, 1962:229). "The code of behaviour between relatives is sanctioned by a belief that any infringement of its provisions will result in retaliation by the spirits, who cause such diseases as leprosy, or who will inflict dire punishment after death and make it impossible for funeral ceremonies to be duly carried out" (Culshaw, 1949: 88).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: "Ideas are also held about punishment in the future life. This is reserved for

those who have gone scot-free in this world. Those who were greedy are made to carry baskets of dung on their heads. Special tortures are also in store for those who wilfully shirk the payment of their debts, and above all for those who transgress the tribal code of sexual morality as well as for those who fail to show the traditional tribal marks on their bodies" (Culshaw, 1949:159).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: "As regards the period of such punishment and re-birth on earth for those who are consigned to Hell, some believe that they are born again as beasts and birds on the earth. But if their sin is washed away completely, they can have re-birth as men. Others are disposed to believe that the sinners never come back to earth as men, but only as birds and beasts" (Mukherjea, 1962:229).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst lesser Bongas under this head, mention should be made of Aclacli Bonga (or Jodhe Bonga as in Mayurbhanj), who presides over the interests of married women. We were told that if a woman steals anything from her parents' home, and takes it to her husband's place, this godling maintains a close watch over the stolen properties and punishes the household by bringing illness and even death" (Mukherjea, 1962:282).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst lesser Bongas under this head, mention should be made of Aclacli Bonga (or Jodhe Bonga as in Mayurbhanj), who presides over the interests of married women. We were told that if a woman steals anything from her parents' home, and takes it to her husband's place, this godling maintains a close watch over the stolen properties and punishes the household by bringing illness and even death" (Mukherjea, 1962:282).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding supernatural reward.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The Heaven (Serma disom, lit. sky-country) is situated up in the blue skies. It is also called Svòròg. There the gods, Maran Buru (the Chief Presiding Deity) and others live. At times they also come down to earth. When after a man's death, his jan baba (bones) are thrown into the sacred river. Damodar, his mul (shadow, soul) goes up to Serma disom or Svòròg (Heaven). There it is that the virtuous ones remain, enjoying heavenly bliss along with the gods themselves" (Mukherjea, 1962:228).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As exemplified in the following excerpt, the Santal religion is bound up with social cohesion and norms. "The Santal religion in its social aspect is essentially a tribal matter and has helped to strengthen the social unity and quicken the sense of social responsibility, and his concept of righteousness is bound up with his social or tribal consciousness" (Biswas, 1956:104).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Each clan possessed a particular food taboo. "There is indeed some taboo in the use by the particular sub-clan of the plant and animal venerated as its ancestor. The animal and plant thus venerated are taboo to the clans; none can hunt it, nor can they partake of its flesh. But because of the observation of this taboo the Santals are in no sense plant and animal worshippers" (Biswas, 1956:106).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required physical risk taking.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: While small-scale rituals are present (see Culshaw, 1949:83), it does not appear that participation is mandatory.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The Santals have a number of religious and semi-religious festivals. It seems as if the very heart of the tribe beats in unison with the advent of these tribal events, for it is here that the Santal plunges into his primitive herd-life to worship the tribal deities, to sing the advent of the agricultural season, to make merry over a bumper crop and to ward off by magic, the pests that hinder the sweet and even flow of their common life" (Mukherjea, 1962:233). "In the Santal villages there is a succession of festivals throughout the year, nearly all connected with agricultural operations. The chief of these is the Sohrae or Banda parab or the harvest festival, celebrated in the Bengali month Pous (i.e., at the beginning of the month of January) after the rice crop of the year has been harvested. This festival generally lasts for five days" (Biswas, 1956:138).

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The priest (Naika) leads animal sacrifices during communal ceremonies (see Biswas, 1956:138).

Is there use of intoxicants:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Santal have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In the Bankura district a missionary has always been a member of the Santal Education Board of the district, and from the beginning the mission sought to establish primary schools in the villages. Openings were found in centres either where some people had been baptized or where some of the influential villagers desired to see a school for the education of their children...The government also found it convenient to rely on the help of missions and has made extensive educational work possible through grants. In the Bankura district Santal children can pass from their village schools to middle schools at Sarenga, and some have subsequently been able to go to High School and a mission College in the district town" (Culshaw, 1949:165).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: "In the Bankura district the number of non-Christian girls who have attended the schools is very small, and none at all have so far attended the boarding school at Sarenga, although Christian and non-Christian boys mingle happily in the boy's school" (Culshaw, 1949:165).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: "The Majhistan or raised platform is an important place for the Santals. They build this place generally, in the centre of the village, near the Manjhi Haram's (headman) house. On it taxes are collected by the Manjhi Haram and legal disputes are settled. There is no fixed size for the Majhistan. It is found that the Santals, in different villages make Majhisthans of different dimensions" (Biswas, 1956:14).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 10, Police), "police functions are specialized and institutionalized on at least some level or levels of political integration."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 9, Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is vested in a functionary or functionaries who are appointed by the supreme executive and/or the supreme deliberative body but are at least relatively independent of the appointing authority."

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "...the Santals have no written script of their own..." (Mukherjea, 1962:7).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "As regards literacy, the ratio (according to the Census of 1931) stands at 9 literates per 1,000 of the same age and sex above 7 years of age, there being 3 literates in English per 10,000 of the same age and sex" (Mukherjea, 1962:61).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Based on the following information, it appears that English is present but not widely used. "As regards literacy, the ratio (according to the Census of 1931) stands at 9 literates per 1,000 of the same age and sex above 7 years of age, there being 3 literates in English per 10,000 of the same age and sex" (Mukherjea, 1962:61).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Santal rely predominantly on intensive, irrigated agriculture for subsistence. Fishing, hunting, and animal husbandry also supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Santal rely predominantly on intensive, irrigated agriculture for subsistence. Fishing, hunting, and animal husbandry also supplement the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.